

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Description of Acute Respiratory Infection in Children at Sukorame Health Centre, Kediri, East Java 2021

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ABSTRACT

Background: Acute respiratory infection is an event that causes high levels of death and morbidity worldwide. Each year, the death rate due to acute respiratory infection reaches 4 million people and 98% of these deaths are due to lower respiratory tract infections. This study describes the distribution of acute respiratory infection incidents among toddlers in the Sukorame Health Centre in 2021. **Methods:** This is a descriptive observational study. Located at Sukorame Health Centre, Kediri City. Data collection took place over three weeks, from 10 to 29 January 2022. **Results:** Age group less than 1 year, the highest number of cases occurred in cases of non-infectious cough, with a total of 459 cases, and in cases of infection, with 39 cases. The gender with the highest number of cases was men diagnosed with cough rather than pneumonia, with a total of 910 cases, and men also had the highest number of cases diagnosed with pneumonia, with a total of 83 cases. In women, 749 cases of non-infectious cough were diagnosed and 61 cases of infection. The areas with the highest number of cases are Bujel subdistrict (387 cases) and Bandar Lor subdistrict (333 cases). **Conclusion:** Infection at the age of 1-5 years is greater than at age <1 year. Both men and women have the same percentage of infections. The highest infection rate is in Bujel sub-district.

Keywords: Acute Respiratory Infection, Children, Description, Health Center

INTRODUCTION

Sukorame Health Centre is a health centre located in the western part of Kediri City. The total working area of Sukorame Health Centre is 12,528 km² divided into 5 sub-district areas, namely Sukorame, Mojoroto, Pojok, Bujel and Bandar Lor (Sukorame Health Centre, 2021).

Based on the 2021 disease trend data at the Community Health Centre, there are 10 diseases with the highest number of cases, namely hypertension 2,900 cases, acute respiratory infections 1,813 cases, diabetes mellitus 1,679 cases, obesity 1,609 cases, gastritis and duodenitis 1,202 cases, other rheumatoid arthritis 878 cases, pharyngitis 575 cases, fever of

unknown cause 513 cases, allergic skin disease 436 cases and heart failure 368 cases.

Acute respiratory infection is an event that causes high levels of death and morbidity worldwide (Aumeya, 2021). Each year, the death rate due to this infection reaches 4 million people and 98% of these deaths are due to lower respiratory tract infections (WHO, 2020).

Acute respiratory infection is caused by viruses or bacteria. This is an infection of the respiratory tract, either the upper or lower respiratory tract, and can cause a wide range of diseases from mild infections to severe and fatal diseases (Aprilla and Yahya, 2019).

Based on the results of basic health research (Riskesdas 2018), the prevalence of

acute respiratory infection in Indonesia is 9.3%, of which 9.0% are males and 9.7% are females (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2018). The highest prevalence of acute respiratory infection occurs in the one to four year age group, which is 13.7% (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2018). The highest number of acute respiratory infection cases in Indonesia occurred in East Nusa Tenggara province 15.4%, Papua 13.1%, Banten 11.9%, West Nusa Tenggara 11.7% and Bali 9.7% (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2018).

In 2020, there were 77,203 cases of pneumonia and 687,098 cases of non-pneumonia cough in East Java province (East Java Health Profile, 2020). In the city of Kediri, the prevalence of pneumonia was 46.6% and 6,681 cases of non-pneumonia cough were recorded. A preliminary study was conducted at Sukorame Community Health Centre, where the number of acute respiratory infection cases in children under five years of age was 144 for pneumonia and 1,389 for non-pneumonia cough.

The number of acute respiratory infection cases found at Sukorame Community Health Centre consists of several classifications of these diseases, namely pneumonia and non-pneumonia cough. The distribution of these cases is mostly in the infant age group of less than 5 years. This is because young children have a body condition that makes them susceptible to disease. This study describes the distribution of acute respiratory infection incidents among toddlers in the Sukorame Health Center in 2021.

METHODS

This is a descriptive observational study. Located at Sukorame Health Centre, Veteran Street No. 50 A Mojototo District, Kediri City. Data collection took place over three weeks, from 10 to 29 January 2022.

Data collection techniques were carried out using secondary and primary data. The

secondary data used are the disease trends in 2021, organisational structure and profile of the Sukorame Health Centre. Primary data was obtained from interviews with acute respiratory infection programme holders at the Sukorame Health Centre.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Most cases occurred in the age group 1 to less than 5 years, both with a diagnosis of non-infectious cough (930 cases) and with a diagnosis of infection (105 cases). Meanwhile, in the age group less than 1 year, the highest number of cases occurred in cases of non-infectious cough, with a total of 459 cases, and in cases of infection, with 39 cases.

The gender with the highest number of cases was men diagnosed with cough rather than pneumonia, with a total of 910 cases, and men also had the highest number of cases diagnosed with pneumonia, with a total of 83 cases. In women, 749 cases of non-infectious cough were diagnosed and 61 cases of infection.

The areas with the highest number of cases are Bujel subdistrict (387 cases) and Bandar Lor subdistrict (333 cases). Mojoroto subdistrict had 284 cases. Pojok sub-district (275 cases) and Sukorame sub-district (254 cases) are low.

Acute respiratory infection is the second most common disease in the community around the Sukorame Health Centre. Acute respiratory infection can be fatal if not treated immediately. The majority of people suffering from acute respiratory infection at Sukorame Health Centre are in the 0-5 age group that is susceptible to viruses or bacteria that enter the body (Fibrila, 2020). The child's age is the main predisposing factor that determines the severity and extent of respiratory infections. Nutritional status also plays a role in the development of the disease. This is related to the child's immune response.

Figure 1. Distribution of acute respiratory infections

Based on the research findings of Fibrila (2020), it shows that young children at high risk (6-12 months) are statistically 5,320 times more likely to experience acute respiratory infection than young children at low risk (Fibrila, 2020). Another study conducted by Putri and Andrian (2018) found that there was a significant relationship ($p=0.013$) between age characteristics and cases of acute respiratory infection in children under five (Putri and Adriyani, 2018). The study conducted by Ranantha, et al (2014) differs from others in that it shows that there is no relationship between age and the incidence of acute respiratory infection in young children (Ranantha, Mahawati and Kun, 2014).

The results show that the incidence of acute respiratory infection tends to be higher in males, namely 910 cases (65.5%) for non-pneumonic cough and 83 (57.6%) for pneumonia.

Male infants have a 5,641 times higher risk of contracting acute respiratory infection compared to female infants (Putri and Adriyani, 2018). Based on research conducted by Darsono, et al (2018), males are 1,655 times more likely to experience risk factors for acute respiratory infection compared to females (Darsono, Novalia and Suwarni, 2018). This is in line with the research by Utami, et al (2018), which states that there are significant differences between male and female acute respiratory infection sufferers.

One theory that may explain how gender may influence the incidence of acute respiratory infection is hormonal differences between men and women (Falagas et. al, 2007). The role of genetics is very important in influencing the immune system, especially at an early age (Utami et. al 2018). The number of X chromosomes determine a person's sex, with women having XX and men having XY chromosomes.

Based on research published by BioEssays, it was found that the X chromosome has microRNAs which play an important role in immunity and cancer. MicroRNAs are small strands of ribonucleic acid, DNA and proteins that also have an important role in the formation of macromolecules for life. The greater number of X chromosomes found in women also causes differences in the number of MicroRNAs which are found more in women than men (Sri, 2014). Another mechanism regarding the relationship between gender and the incidence of ISPA could be caused by the factor that boys tend to be more active than girls, thereby allowing boys to be more frequently exposed to agents that cause ISPA (Iskandar, Tanuwijaya and Yuniarti, 2015).

Risk factors for acute respiratory infection disease are environmental factors. Environment This refers to indoor and outdoor air pollution and household hygiene. Environmental factors include: indoor air pollution (cigarette smoke, mosquito coil smoke and smoke from burning fuel for cooking in high concentrations), house ventilation and housing density (Trilia and Istinengtiyas, 2021).

The indoor environment closely interacts with the place of daily life of young children: if the indoor environment where a family gathers and takes shelter is unhealthy due to infectious attacks by bacteria or viruses, it can cause various diseases in young children, one of which is acute respiratory infection (Putri Lan Lubis and Ferusgel, 2019). On the other hand, outdoor pollution such as combustion, traffic, and factory emissions. The indoor environment is closely related to the daily living space of toddlers. If the home environment, where a family gathers and takes shelter, is unhealthy due to bacterial or viral infections, it can cause various diseases in infants, one of which is acute respiratory infection (Jayanti, Ashar and Aulia, 2018).

The areas with the highest number of cases are Bujel sub-district (387 cases) and Bandar Lor sub-district (333 cases). This is because the

environmental conditions in the areas of Bujel and Bandar Lor subdistricts are very congested. In addition, many residential areas still have cement floors, which can easily become a breeding ground for disease.

In a densely populated environment, air circulation and light ingress into the home may prevent the air in the home from leaving the room. In Putri and Farugel (2019), it was found that there was a significant relationship between ventilation and the incidence in children.

According to Titi Saparina, et al (2020), substandard environmental conditions, especially unhealthy housing, have a major impact on the body's immune system. Housing that is dirty, cramped, overcrowded and lacks adequate clean water facilities often exposes children to germs from dirty places and ultimately leads to various infectious diseases. Houses that do not have enough clean air flow and whose inhabitants often inhale the smoke that collects in the house, will easily get acute respiratory infection (Titi Saparina et. al, 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

The incidence of acute respiratory infection based on the age distribution in the working area of Sukorame Community Health Centre is that it mainly occurs in young children aged 1 to less than 5 years in both non-pneumonic and pneumonic cough classifications. This age group has a body that is susceptible to contracting diseases due to the influence of the body's fragile immunity. In addition, in this group, babies have started to do a lot of activities in the outside environment.

Acute respiratory infection incidence based on gender distribution in the work area Sukorame Health Centre, which often occurs in male infants. This is due to the fact that boys tend to be more active than girls, so boys are more likely to be exposed to the agents that cause acute respiratory infection.

Acute respiratory infection incidents based on location/sub-district in the Sukorame Health Centre working area, namely mostly in Bujel and Bndar Lor sub-districts. This is because the population is densely populated and many people still use cement floors, which makes the air easily moist and can become a breeding ground for disease.

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